

TalX Workshop 2: Adaptation Leadership for Well-Adapting Places

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Introduction

A changing climate poses a wide range of impacts and risks for the UK and Ireland. To prepare for these climatic impacts, dynamic and sustainable adaptation action is needed across all sectors and tiers of society. This needs to be underpinned by an increase in the capacity of organisations and communities to deliver adaptation actions in different places across Britain and Ireland.

As part of the EPA-funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TaIX) project, an adaptation Capability and Maturity Model (CMM) is being created for Britain and Ireland (Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England) that will enable and support the development of adaptation capability for the purposes of enhancing and accelerating place-based adaptation action. This model will be targeted at adaptation practitioners, provide a practical framework that supports a combination of top-down and bottom-up adaptation measures. Moreover, the model will act as a roadmap to enhance adaptation capability and enable progression on the journey towards a well-adapted place.

To develop the CMM a series of co-creation workshops are being held online that invite experienced adaptation practitioners and policymakers from across the Britain and Ireland to provide their insights and experiences of 'on the ground' adaptation and the capabilities required to deliver effective adaptation. The first of these workshops (practitioner perspectives on well-adapting places) was held on March 29th and 30th and invited practitioners from across the jurisdictions to identified priority capability themes for inclusion in the CMM. The priority themes identified included:

- Leadership and Ownership (**Leadership**)
- Research, Knowledge and Expertise (**Evidence**)
- Collaboration, Cross-Sectoral Networks and Partnerships (**Partnerships**)
- Community Education, Engagement, Involvement and Empowerment (**Community**)
- Sustained and Secure Funding and Resource (**Resource**)

For each priority theme, a dedicated workshop is being held (Figure 1) to explore each theme in detail.

Figure 1: Themes in the Workshop Series with the theme of this workshop (Leadership) report outlined in red

Workshop 2 - Leadership

The second TalX workshop was held on the 7th of July 2021 and based the priority theme 'Leadership'. The workshop aimed to establish the key leadership qualities needed for good place-based adaptation and the actions and activities necessary to develop this leadership. The workshop was targeted at experienced climate adaptation practitioners from across the 5 jurisdiction areas (Appendix 1).

There are multiple definitions of Leadership for climate adaptation in the literature. For the purposes of this workshop Leadership is being defined as:

'Leading the way by setting goals, advocating and resourcing initiatives on adaptation. Those who possess this capability are champions and agents of change, who drive others to engage and participate in adaptation actions.'

The purpose of this workshop was to draw out the nuances of leadership in terms of both attributes and actions, and at different stage of adaptation.

Workshop Structure

To support workshop activities and prior to the workshop, a [pre-recorded video](#) was circulated to all participants which provides an overview of the TalX project. The workshop was delivered online over one afternoon and included a series of introductory presentations and two work sessions (WS) (Figures 2, 3 & 4).

Introductory Presentations:

The presentations provided a brief overview of climate adaptation leadership, the challenges that occur, how different organisations face these challenges and the types of leadership styles that can be employed, setting the scene for the subsequent work sessions and the discussions on leadership.

The keynote speaker, Robert Kay, deputy director of the ICF Climate Center in California, presented on leadership in climate change adaptation in California (Figure 2). He discussed the challenges they faced, in particular with regard to providing justice and equity for everyone when designing and implementing adaptation measures and the dangers of assumed perfection when looking at adaptation measures in those places considered to be leaders in climate adaptation.

Following this, case studies on leadership from Ireland (David Dodd), Northern Ireland (Cathy Burns) and Scotland (James Curran) were then presented (Figure 3). The Irish case study focused on the role of the Climate Action Regional Offices (CARO's) in supporting climate action at the local authority scale in the Republic of Ireland. The Northern Irish case study explored the efforts of the Derry and Strabane council, who are the first council to develop a climate action plan in Northern Ireland, in developing and implementing and adaptation plan with limited resource. The Scottish case study centred around the Climate Ready Clyde initiative and the importance of authentic leadership in engaging stakeholders, allowing for multi-partner solutions and co-benefits.

Figure 2: An illustration showing information on the workshop series and key note presentation

Figure 3: An illustration showing information on the case study examples of leadership across Britain and Ireland

Work Session 1:

WS1 focused on leadership qualities in adaptation, identifying what leadership qualities participants felt were necessary to develop good place-based climate adaptation. This was achieved through a structured exercise employing Miro, a prioritisation exercise conducted through Slido, and a plenary discussion.

Work Session 2:

WS2 involved two inter-related tasks, encouraging participants to think about what actions and activities they have performed to help them develop leadership, and how these have evolved over time as adaptation progresses. Both tasks were carried out using Miro, employing structured information gathering and maturity mapping exercises, and following this, discussions in breakout groups.

Figure 4: An illustration showing the layout of the work sessions

Results

The presentations on leadership addressed various aspects, opportunities and challenges of leadership faced by practitioners in different locations and at different stages of adaptation development. The work sessions were coordinated via Miro, where the outputs of the working sessions are stored. They are available at: [TaIX Workshop July 07th, Online Whiteboard for Visual Collaboration](#) (miro.com). The insights and outputs for each of these are summarised below:

Work Session 1 – Qualities of Leadership

WS1 highlighted the qualities the participants considered necessary for good leadership in climate adaptation, which have been grouped thematically for ease of understanding and to avoid duplication. There were 22 themes identified (Appendix 3), and 5 clearly prioritised by participants (The Ability to Work with Others/Approachable; Providing Structure and Governance; Communication and Understanding; Honesty and Authenticity; and Informed) through a Slido poll (Appendix 4).

Of the leadership qualities identified, all are valuable for individual leadership, but many are also applicable to institutional/organisational leadership. This suggests that the participants consider individual leadership qualities, and the development of these qualities in climate champions, important for successful organisational leadership progression. In other words, ‘it is the people that make the place’.

Through the prioritization of leadership qualities, we can see that the ability to collaborate and provide structure and governance are considered as key leadership qualities necessary for successful climate adaptation. These qualities lean more towards organisational than individual leadership which suggests that there is a higher consideration given to organisational leadership, which has the potential to influence policy and push for more significant change on a larger scale, benefitting a greater number of people.

Figure 5: An illustration depicting the key leadership qualities and priority actions and activities

Work Session 2 – Actions of Leadership

WS2 identified the actions that participants had taken to develop good leadership and involved a maturity mapping exercise discussing how the leadership quality themes identified in WS1 evolve over time (Figures 6-9).

In terms of activities, there were several key themes that the participants felt had helped them develop leadership in climate adaptation (Appendix 5), these activities have been classified as those activities relating to: raising awareness and buy in; realistic expectations and strategy; emotional connection; vision; knowledge and information; embracing innovation; mainstreaming; understanding and awareness; instilling belief; and networking and communication. There was some overlap in WS1 and WS2, with many of the actions identified in WS2 building on and progressing the qualities prioritised in WS1. The maturity mapping exercise discussed how leadership actions identified earlier in WS2 evolve over time. Each group discussed actions that they felt helped them develop leadership in their adaptation journey from those just starting out, right through to a mature well-adapted place, ‘implementing on the ground’ action (Appendix 6).

Stages of maturity in climate adaptation leadership have been split into 4 different levels which are described below:

Level 1

Leaders that considers the perspectives of all stakeholders on what good adaptation looks like in the ‘place’ and lay the groundwork for future action.

Level 2

Established in climate adaptation with agreed principles of working, leaders have a vision beyond the immediate future and the ability to see cross-sectoral linkages.

Level 3

Charismatic and authentic climate champions throughout organisations who make links between climate action and social change and use tailored communication to engage the audience.

Level 4

Going beyond individual to institutional leadership, were core values on climate justice and resilience as well as sustainable environmental, economic and social development are embedded in the culture of the ‘place’.

To progress through each of these stages different attributes and actions of leadership have been identified as necessary at each level.

Level 1

Attributes: The main attributes of leadership when starting out on the adaptation planning journey include a passion for progressing climate adaptation, someone who chooses to lead because they consider proactive adaptation as essential. These individuals are not necessarily experts in climate adaptation, but are willing to learn and work with others to address their knowledge gaps in order to understand and effectively use the available evidence and data. They also have the ability to establish structures to work within and keep staff motivated.

Actions: At this stage, leaders can further develop adaptation capability through the recruitment of the appropriate people who are climate adaptation champions. They ensure staff remain motivated by setting out realistic ambitions and targets and ensuring there is an effective structure in place to achieve these. Leaders can use government policy and strategy as well as established climate organisations/initiatives to encourage engagement and education, provide evidence and information and support collaboration and wider thinking, developing the organisations they are a part of as they go.

Figure 6: Specific actions for those fostering leadership in the beginning stage of adaptation

Level 2

Attributes: Leaders at this stage of their adaptation journey have the ability to see the bigger picture, including cross-sectoral linkages, the interfaces between national and local adaptation, and are not focused only on their own specific remit. They have the knowledge and experience and a contextual vision, that goes beyond evidence and data. These leaders trust those they work with and are not afraid to delegate within their team.

Actions: Building a strong team with agreed working principles helps leaders at this stage to avoid an overreliance on specific individuals. Understanding potential avenues of funding, identifying priority

areas for adaptation and creating a strategy for action supports adaptation progress. By utilizing climate organisations to encourage wider involvement and joining with larger groups to raise the profile of adaptation in their ‘place’ leaders can help establish a vision beyond the immediate future.

Figure 7: Specific actions for those fostering leadership in the developing stage of adaptation

Level 3

Attributes: Leaders at this stage of adaptation are energetic and charismatic, with the ability to connect people, recognise and respect different perspective and engage in reasonable debate. These leaders are knowledge brokers with an in-depth understanding of the ‘wicked problem’ that climate adaptation represents.

Actions: To progress adaptation at this stage leaders need to make links between climate actions and social change, tailoring communication to various audiences and connecting on both an intellectual and emotional level. By appointing enthusiastic climate champions across different departments and ensuring the coordination of responsibilities, leaders can connect with new audiences and initiate cross-sectoral policy alignment. The continued development of finance and resource will provide stability within organisations while networking initiatives will promote adaptation. By recognising those who aren’t stereotypical climate champion and the value they add as well as encouraging reflective stakeholder practices, leaders can allow more voices to be heard and acknowledged, providing more representative views and supporting a more equitable progression of adaptation.

Figure 8: Specific actions for those fostering leadership in the robust stage of adaptation

Level 4

Attributes: Leadership in this stage has moved beyond the individual, to institutional leadership. Everyone is prepared to be a passionate champion for climate action and positive change, willing to go the extra mile to include the disenfranchised and ensure a just transition. Core values on climate justice and resilience are embedded in organisational culture alongside the ideals of sustainable environmental, economic and social development and organisations have the courage and conviction to say no to mal-adaptative measures, even under pressure from stakeholders.

Actions: At this stage of adaptation there should be an over-arching vision that drives transformational change that extends beyond typical geographical boundaries. By integrating adaptation into all aspects of governance and embracing collaboration and the co-benefits, adaptation can be accelerated. Incorporating diversity at senior levels of leadership and selecting those people who are best for different aspects of adaptation (planning/delivery) enables a representative view of adaptation action across different 'places'.

Figure 9: Specific actions for those fostering leadership in the optimising stage of adaptation

Conclusions

The workshop helped draw out insights and information on leadership from the experiences of the participants in adaptation planning and actions across different places in Britain and Ireland. In doing so, the workshop identified the challenges of leadership faced by both those beginning adaptation initiatives (e.g. getting organisational buy-in and resource to begin adaptation actions) and those at more advanced stages of adaptation (e.g. changing ingrained behaviours within an organisation to develop more innovative and effective adaptation processes).

The workshop highlighted that adaptation leadership must delve into social issues, in particular issues around equity, justice and inclusion in order to be successful and how challenging this can be. There was a strong belief that there has to be systemic, sustainable change, with a 'no one left behind policy' and that this cannot be dependent on the actions of a few specific individuals/figureheads, but rather through a network of leaders. There was also confirmed the need for a strategic vision that has integrated and recognized all voices in the community, not just the loudest, and that while ambition is encouraged, this needs to be tempered with realistic actions based on available resources and clear communication to the public by those in leadership roles.

The TalX team would like to thank all the attendees and especially the speakers, for their active participation and willingness to share their insights and experience in order to promote and enable climate adaptation actions in Britain and Ireland.

Appendix 1: Participant list for the workshop

Workshop 2- Leadership		
Participant	Country - Organisation	Country
Robert Kay	Deputy Director of ICF's Climate Centre	USA
David Dodd	Head of Dublin CARO	Ireland
Alan Dunney	Head of Eastern and Midlands CARO	Ireland
Sabrina Dekker	Dublin City County Council	Ireland
Breda Maher	Kildare County Council	Ireland
Darby Mullen	South Dublin County Council	Ireland
Caroline Corrigan	Meath County Council	Ireland
Margaret Desmond	Environmental Protection Agency	Ireland
Clive Walmsley	Natural Resources Wales	Wales
Ben Sears	Welsh Government	Wales
Matt Ellis	Environment Agency	England
Kerrell Whalley	Climate Change Manager at Wigan	England
Kate Lonsdale	University of Leeds	England
James Curran	Chair of Climate Ready Clyde	Scotland
Lesley Hinshelwood	South Lanarkshire Council	Scotland
Emma Whitham	Project Manager of Highland Adapts	Scotland
Kate Crowley	Lecturer in Climate Risk and Resilience University of Edinburgh	Scotland
Craig Love	Climate change and sustainability manager at Transport Scotland	Scotland
Tara Murray	Aberdeenshire Council	Scotland
Cathy Burns	Derry City and Strabane District Council	Northern Ireland
Richard McLernon	Project Co-ordinator for Resilient Belfast at Belfast City Council	Northern Ireland

TalX Workshop: Leadership as a key capability for place-based climate adaptation

Date: July 7th 2021

Venue: Online-Microsoft Teams

Background: To develop a capability maturity model (CMM) that can be applied across Britain and Ireland to support effective place-based adaptation, the EPA-funded TalX project (<https://talx.ie/>) is holding a series of workshops to explore different capabilities which can enable 'good' place-based climate adaptation.

Purpose: The 2nd workshop in the series will be held online on July 7th 2021 and will focus on 'Leadership', a key capability required in order to progress climate adaptation. The work will focus on determining the key characteristics of good leadership and the actions required to progress these qualities over time in order to deliver successful place-based adaptation.

'Leadership is seen as leading the way by setting goals, advocating and resourcing initiatives on adaptation. Those who possess this capability are champions and agents of change, who drive others to engage and participate in adaptation actions.'

We will be joined at the workshop by Robert Kay, deputy director of the ICF's Climate Centre, to share his insights on leadership and his experience with the development of a framework of adaptation capabilities for use by local authorities in California.

Useful Information:

- In advance of the workshop and to make the most efficient use of time available, participants are asked to view a video presentation providing an overview of the TalX project. The video presentation has been made available [here](#)
- To support workshop activities, the MIRO and Mentimeter platforms will be employed. You can find a short introductory video on how to use Miro [here](#) and Mentimeter [here](#)

Access to the Workshop:

The workshop will be held online and through Microsoft Teams, the following links can be used to access the workshop. Please note that workshop proceedings will be recorded for research purposes.

- [Teams Link for Workshop 2, \(7th July\)](#)

Workshop Agenda:

Workshop 2 (Wednesday July 7th, 2021):

Time	Title	Presenter
14:00	Welcome, Introductions and Overview	Barry O'Dwyer/Denise McCullagh
14:10	Climate Change Adaptation in California	Robert Kay
14:30	Case study examples of successful leadership and lessons learned	Multiple
15:00	Work Session 1: What is good leadership for place-based adaptation?	All
15:30	Break	
15:35	Work Session 2: How to develop good leadership to enable adaptation action	All
16:20	Wrap up and Close	All

Appendix 3: Summary of WS1 results: What are leadership qualities needed for good climate adaptation?

Leadership Quality Theme	Individual Attributes	Organisational Attributes
Ability to work with others/Approachable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personable • Relatable • Approachable • Respectful • Ability to negotiate and collaborate • Networking • Ability to work with others and facilitate high quality connections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reachable and not intimidating potential participants • Bring in people that offer a new and/or different view and can challenge the status quo • Ability to negotiate and collaborate • Ability to work with others and facilitate high quality connections
Provides structure and Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitative leadership and skills • Provides a clear vision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creates structures and Governance • Facilitative leadership and skills • Provides a clear vision
Communication and Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills – communicate clearly in plain language, creating a compelling narrative • Presents clearly the complexity of the challenge • Good presentation skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presents clearly the complexity of the challenge
Honesty and Authenticity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentic • Honesty • Integrity • Trustful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading by example • Transparency
Informed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed • Understands the wicked nature of the challenge • Knowledge broker – Someone who can speak across topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed
Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active listening skills • Empathy and understanding • Emotional intelligence 	
Enabling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coaching not dictating • Enabling of others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage reflection on action for continuous improvement • Training
Ability to join the dots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good interpreter of facts – engaging • Ability to join the dots • Strategic thinker and vision maker 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic thinking and vision making
Resilient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strength of character • Courage • Willpower • Resilience – thick skinned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resilience and the ability to overcome obstacles and setbacks
Adaptable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptable and using adaptative leadership • Ability to act with partial information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change management • Willingness to accept and embrace transformational change
Trustworthy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trustworthy • Credibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credibility
Sustainable leadership for the long-term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humility and self-knowledge – Recognition of your shortcomings • Dedication to the issue of providing leadership • Commitment that goes beyond fancy slogans and campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability to maintain all aspects of leadership (individual, organisational and capacity building) • Dedication to the issue of providing leadership • Commitment that goes beyond fancy slogans and campaigns
Open to new ideas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-minded • Open to new ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative and open to new solutions and ways of working

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding and appreciating all perspectives 	
Ambitious	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ambition Acknowledging that we need to look beyond the local – we are global citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to see beyond the political spectrum Acknowledging that we need to look beyond the local – we are global citizens
Clarity of the scope of leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time specifically for leadership Visibility Relevance Energetic – Stamina Ability to lead change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visibility Ability to lead change
Appreciates the need for research as well as monitoring and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizon-scanning – Planning ahead Appreciates the need for new research and not just monitoring and evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizon-scanning – Planning ahead Appreciates the need for new research and not just monitoring and evaluation
Celebrates success and change makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Celebrate the work of others as well as your own 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Celebrates change makers
Accountable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accepting responsibility Courage to make difficult decisions and stand over them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Everyone taking accountability/responsibility both in and out of work
Charismatic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passionate – A true belief that we need to tackle the climate crisis together Enthusiasm Influencer Charisma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Passionate – A true belief that we need to tackle the climate crisis together
Flexible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creative Flexibility in approach and ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility in approach and ideas
Not alarmist but a realist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realistic Willing to listen and understand practical limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourages realism rather than rhetoric Defined strategy and goals that are set to a realistic timeline Recognises that rigid protocols can get in the way
Consistent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consistent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consistent

Appendix 4: Slido Poll

Appendix 5: Summary of WS2 results: What steps did you take on your journey to shaping a well-adapted place?

Theme	Individual Actions/Activities	Organisational Actions/Activities
Diversity & Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading an inclusive theory of change process • Inclusion • Work with the coalition of the willing • Recognising the strength of those who have multidisciplinary experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure diversity (e.g. race, gender, disciplines, skill etc) in senior positions to ensure all of society is represented • Create opportunities for other to have their say – Opening doors • Co-development and implementation of projects with a range of leaders • Recognising the strength of those who have multidisciplinary experience
Raising awareness/ Buy-In	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the right people are in the room • Awareness raising • Seek organizational backing of available services (e.g. Climate NI, CARO's etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working to get cross-sectoral and organizational buy-in • Get those in leadership roles on board to allow others to participate more easily • Work closely with interested elected officials – assist them to bring their colleagues on board
Realistic Expectations/Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning to see a clear pathway • Be realistic about what can be achieved and communicate this clearly • Clear remit of what we are going to do and what we are not going to do • Be transparent about inconvenience and accept and explain that there will issues and challenges • Have ambition – but temper this with realism to keep people motivated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning to see a clear pathway • Break adaptation down into sizeable chunks that departments can do • Time pressures from funding can catalyse action • Be transparent about inconvenience and accept and explain that there will issues and challenges
Emotional Connection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect at an emotional level – Make it personal • Use emotive language – (e.g. future generations) that keep people invested • Build trust by taking action locally • Be personable – work with all of society (young and old) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use multi-media/illustrations to show the impacts of climate change locally and help people understand how it affects them directly • Recognising that those with a climate science background are not necessarily the ones that can make things relevant and real to people • Use emotive language – (e.g. future generations) that keep people invested

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognising that those with a climate science background are not necessarily the ones that can make things relevant and real to people 	
Vision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vision of where you want to get to and scope of what you can do Vision sprint – day in the life 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use imagery to show your vision – be creative Vision of where you want to get to and scope of what you can do
Knowledge/information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing knowledge Synthesis of Information Understanding the level of knowledge people will have 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elected members provide correct information to their constituents Synthesis of Information Understanding the level of knowledge people will have Sharing knowledge
Embracing innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognise that sometimes starting from scratch can be easier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embracing new ideas and technology Develop exemplar climate action projects Workshops that include blue skies thinking exercises
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training programmes to develop leadership skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upskilling to allow action ‘on the ground’ Management courses Climate action leadership programme for senior staff and elected members Vocational training for early career professionals- Focus on climate and risk leadership – Specific professional courses for climate risk LA Climate Action 6 Pillar - Training programme Workshop by KIT England for council employees Training programmes to develop leadership skills
Mainstreaming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear and visible linking of agenda’s Equal attention to adaptation and mitigation Clear articulation of the benefits and co-benefits of adaptation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embedded adaptation in strategy and plans Clear and visible linking of agenda’s Establish the political and executive structures required to implement the relevant goals and actions Equal attention to adaptation and mitigation Clear articulation of the benefits and co-benefits of adaptation
Understanding and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-awareness Ability to reflect on challenges and expand thought processes, addressing your own bias Understanding different models of leadership Lead by example 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authentic leadership- accepting what you don’t know and recognizing rigid practices won’t work Building confidence by getting your own house in order first

Instilling Belief		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that sustainability that is embedded in work is also taken home
Networking & Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent and relevant communication – be truthful and make people aware of inconveniences they will face • Developing networks from working projects and participation in workshops, conferences etc 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared leadership across the local government sector – working with early adaptors to bring others onboard • Small focused steering group membership for leaders in sustainability and business – structured plan development • Engaged with a variety of different stakeholders (e.g. city councils, CCA initiatives, researchers, regulators) • Facilitated process with maximum staff involvement through workshops and feedback • Climate action working groups each led by service managers acting as wider role models • Developing networks from working projects and participation in workshops, conferences etc • Consistent and relevant communication – be truthful and make people aware of inconveniences they will face

Appendix 6: Summary of WS2 results - Maturity mapping of leadership attributes and actions

Level 1 - Beginning	Level 2 - Intermediate	Level 3 - Robust	Level 4 - Optimising
Ability to set up a structure and ensure continuity of staff	Ability to see cross-sectoral linkages – start to break across boundaries and collaborate – look at longer term plans	When speaking to different audiences give local examples of climate actions – be passionate and know your audience when communicating, whether it be the general public or government officials etc.	Certain individuals on board who never lose sight of the longer term view – not caught up with the short term and now – long-term innovative thinking – cathedral thinking
Recruit the initial members – coalition of the willing – this is generally a network of volunteers across organisations informing and educating will listening to the stories of the public	Choosing the correct leaders is essential for shaping future actions – having no one with expertise or knowledge of adaptation will influence future climate action plans (as is the case for Edinburgh climate commission)	Reflective practice allows more voices to be heard, gives confidence to less confident people and reflecting on what had real value rather than just the loudest voice – representation of the less included	That everyone is a leader/champion for climate action, it's integrated throughout all aspects of everyday working – successful authentic leadership (they've done themselves out of a job) - A total mindset change from authorities, where climate action is considered throughout every action of governance in every sector and the entire structure of organisations embrace it
Set out ambitions – be clear on what adaptation involves and that it is not mitigation	Using organisations like the CARO's to encourage work in groups and beyond your local area	Connecting the heart and the head, using techniques to show that this is something we all care about, to bring all aspects of people's views in	Those in positions of power (particularly elected leaders) are willing to say no to benefit long-term climate action, even when facing public pressure to allow certain things – going well-beyond cost-benefit analysis
Leaders need to lead for everyone – so leaders need to be there for the right reasons (e.g. not just to advance career etc.), passionate and committed to the challenge and demands of the role	Need to use a contextual vision of adaptation, not just hard science and data	Recognising dedication to the cause that the unusual leaders bring, recognising those who aren't the stereotypical leaders and the different types of connections they create and both formal and informal champions	Transformational leadership rather than transactional leadership – looking beyond the 5 year policy/political cycle – potential to consider maladaptation – lock-in decisions) and make good decisions now

Be willing to learn	At this stage leadership tends to rely on the personal capacities of specific individuals – this can cause a vacuum if they change roles	Start to make links between climate action and social change	Change management – creating a culture of change and establishing values of an organisation that everyone works towards – around citizens, natural environment, economic development – core values that permeate through the organisation and its more about coordination and support than leadership
Leadership in the early stages of adaptation tends to be evidence led and based rather than emotionally led	Understand vulnerabilities and being able to prioritise them - Develop a strategic approach across the ‘place’ involved	Transitioning to be a knowledge broker as you grow in confidence and experience – continual learning and confidence in leading initiatives	Need a variety of skills and expertise, genders, races etc. in senior management positions to represent everyone and leave no one behind – make sure there is diversity in leadership
Having policy and strategies available from government to motivate involvement	Develop the ability to build a team around you and delegate	Champion/leaders need to bring energy to the role and connect with new audiences	Thinking and acting beyond geographical boundaries
	Beginning to think beyond short-term political cycles to the direction you want to move climate adaptation – thinking longer term	Have climate champions within departments	Leading a just transition as well as just resilience – not just lip service to these ideals - Going the extra mile to include the disenfranchised -go to them if they aren’t coming to you
	Start to develop finance action – have resources and leadership available and committed – this allows for some stability moving forward	Cross-sectoral policy alignment	Break down traditional professional roles and boundaries and collaboration across the board
	Joining larger groups to increase the profile of adaptation (e.g. Belfast being a Rockefeller 100 city helped bring adaptation to the limelight)	Leadership that is willing to have its thinking challenged	Realising the need to capture and retain tacit knowledge – having passionate staff who believe in what they’re doing and want to stay in the position

	Have agreed principles of working	Charismatic personality – knowledge across multiple sectors and the ability to connect people	A shift in leadership between planning and delivery, different people at different stages of the process – best person for the job
		Everything is well-coordinated, everyone knows what they're doing – and the leaders have concrete climate adaptation action measures in place	